

Volumetric and viscometric properties of urea and D-glucose in aqueous glycine at 308 K

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Density, viscosity and refractive index data for urea and D-glucose in (0.01, 0.02 and 0.03 M) glycine + water mixed solvent as a function of urea/glucose concentration are presented at 308 K. The density data have been used to obtain limiting apparent molar volume (ϕ_v^0) and the slope (S_v^*) using Masson's equation. The viscosity data are analysed by means of Jones-Dole equation. The activation parameters of viscous flow, namely free energy of activation per mole of solvent, ($\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$) and free energy of activation per mole of solute, ($\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$), were obtained by the application of transition-state theory. The refractive index was used to calculate molar refractive index, (R_D) of the solutes in different solvent mixtures. All these parameters are used to study the solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions in the mixtures used in the present investigation.

Amino acids are the fundamental structural units of proteins and thermodynamic and viscometric properties of these model compounds in aqueous medium provide information about solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions which in turn may help to understand several biochemical processes such as protein hydration, denaturation, aggregation etc¹. Amino acids as structural components of proteins, participate in all the physiological processes of a living cell². The solution behaviour of urea is of considerable significance in biophysics³. Urea serves as an effective protein denaturant. Despite of its prominent role in biology, urea continues to intrigue and fascinate solution chemists because of the curious manner in which it affects aqueous solutions³. Glucose is an essential constituent of blood and on reaching the tissues it is oxidised to produce CO₂, water and energy. In view of the practical importance of the above mentioned compounds, an attempt has been made to study the solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions of urea and D-glucose in (0.01, 0.02 and 0.03 M) aqueous glycine solution at 308 K. This temperature is chosen due to its closeness to body temperature. Though there are extensive thermodynamic studies of amino acids in water⁴, very few data are available in aqueous urea/glucose⁵ solutions.

In the present paper we intend to report the densities, ρ , viscosities, η and refractive indices, n_D of (0.01, 0.03, 0.05, 0.07, 0.09 and 0.1 M) urea/D-glucose in (0.01, 0.02 and 0.03 M) glycine in water at 308 K. Experimental values of ρ and η were used to calculate the apparent molar volume, ϕ_v , limiting apparent molar volume, ϕ_v^0 , A and B coefficients of Jones-Dole equation⁶, free energies of activation of viscous flow, $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ and $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ per mole of solvent and solute re-

spectively. n_D values were used to calculate molar refractivity, R_D for all the ternary solvent mixtures. These parameters were interpreted in terms of solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions in the solvent mixtures.

Results and discussion

Measured ρ , η and n_D of 0.01, 0.03, 0.05, 0.07, 0.09 and 0.1 M urea/glucose in (0.01, 0.02 and 0.03 M) glycine + water solvents at 308 K are listed in Table 1. The experi-

Table 1. Densities (ρ), viscosities (η) and refractive indices (n_D) of urea/D-glucose in aqueous glycine as function of concentration (C) of urea/D-glucose at 308 K

C (mol dm ⁻³)	ρ (kg m ⁻³)	η (10 ⁻³ N m ² s)	n_D	ρ (kg m ⁻³)	η (10 ⁻³ N m ² s)	n_D
Urea + 0.01 M glycine			D-Glucose + 0.01 M glycine			
0.0000	0.9942	0.7111	1.3314	0.9943	0.7165	1.3314
0.0100	0.9942	0.7122	1.3321	0.9944	0.7169	1.3318
0.0300	0.9945	0.7132	1.3323	0.9965	0.7264	1.3321
0.0500	0.9950	0.7149	1.3325	0.9979	0.7314	1.3325
0.0700	0.9953	0.7154	1.3331	0.9992	0.7389	1.3329
0.0900	0.9956	0.7162	1.3337	1.0005	0.7452	1.3332
0.1000	0.9957	0.7181	1.3339	1.0012	0.7538	1.3336
Urea + 0.02 M glycine			D-Glucose + 0.02 M glycine			
0.0000	0.9946	0.7122	1.3317	0.9945	0.7238	1.3318
0.0100	0.9946	0.7130	1.3321	0.9955	0.7364	1.3321
0.0300	0.9950	0.7138	1.3326	0.9967	0.7393	1.3326
0.0500	0.9953	0.7155	1.3329	0.9979	0.7441	1.3329
0.0700	0.9957	0.7157	1.3330	0.9995	0.7512	1.3331
0.0900	0.9961	0.7164	1.3333	1.0016	0.7573	1.3337
0.1000	0.9961	0.7166	1.3335	1.0018	0.7673	1.3342

Table-1 (contd.)

Urea + 0.03 M glycine				D-Glucose + 0.03 M glycine		
0.0000	0.9947	0.7222	1.3293	0.9950	0.7239	1.3295
0.0100	0.9949	0.7206	1.3297	0.9957	0.7275	1.3301
0.0300	0.9955	0.7205	1.3300	0.9968	0.7289	1.3308
0.0500	0.9957	0.7151	1.3303	0.9984	0.7361	1.3315
0.0700	0.9960	0.7143	1.3304	0.9996	0.7462	1.3318
0.0900	0.9962	0.7181	1.3305	1.0009	0.7489	1.3321
0.1000	0.9964	0.7229	1.3306	1.0021	0.7544	1.3324

mental values of ρ were used to calculate, ϕ_v using the following standard relation :

$$\phi_v = 1000 (\rho_0 - \rho) / C\rho_0 + M_2/\rho_0 \quad (1)$$

where ρ_0 and ρ are the densities of the solvent and solution respectively, C is the molar concentration of solute (urea/glucose) and M_2 is the molecular weight. The calculated values of ϕ_v are given in Table 2. ϕ_v were calculated by the

Table 2. Apparent molar volume, (ϕ_v) of urea/D-glucose in aqueous glycine as function of concentration (C) of urea/D-glucose at 308 K

C (mol dm ⁻³)	ϕ_v (10 ⁻⁵ m ³ mol ⁻¹)		
	Urea + 0.01 M glycine	Urea + 0.02 M glycine	Urea + 0.03 M glycine
0.0000			
0.0100	6.1214	6.0006	3.7720
0.0300	5.0854	4.6104	3.5015
0.0500	4.4618	4.4747	4.1383
0.0700	4.4819	4.4833	4.2486
0.0900	4.4931	4.3804	4.3975
0.1000	4.5473	4.5159	4.2922
	D-Glucose + 0.01 M glycine	D-Glucose + 0.02 M glycine	D-Glucose + 0.03 M glycine
0.0000			
0.0100	17.1135	8.0603	11.0714
0.0300	10.7439	10.7417	12.0764
0.0500	10.8780	11.2780	11.2724
0.0700	11.0792	10.9333	11.5021
0.0900	11.1909	10.1831	11.5180
0.1000	11.1897	10.7753	10.9709

method of least squares and were fitted to the plots of ϕ_v versus $C^{1/2}$ in accordance with Masson's empirical relation⁷.

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^0 + S_v^* C^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

where S_v^* is the slope of the plots, ϕ_v^0 is a measure of the solute-solvent interactions and S_v^* is the pair interaction parameter which is indicative of solute-solute interactions.

Table 3. Partial molar volume (ϕ_v^0) and its experimental slope (S_v^*) of urea/D-glucose in aqueous glycine at 308 K

Glycine (M/mol dm ⁻³)	ϕ_v^0 (10 ⁻⁵ m ³ mol ⁻¹)	S_v^* (10 ⁻⁵ m ³ mol ^{-3/2} dm ^{1/2})
Urea + aqueous glycine		
0.01	6.5001	-7.1208
0.02	6.1627	-6.1779
0.03	3.2487	3.5265
D-Glucose + aqueous glycine		
0.01	17.1100	-22.1210
0.02	8.1851	9.3357
0.03	11.5390	-0.5960

The calculated values of ϕ_v^0 and S_v^* are given in Table 3. It is evident from Table 3 that ϕ_v^0 values are large positive for both glucose and urea in all the three aqueous glycine mixed solvents, thereby, showing the presence of strong solute-solvent interactions. Thus, both solutes behave as structure makers in glycine + water medium. Table 3 shows that the values of ϕ_v^0 for glucose are larger than those for urea, suggesting that the extent of solute-solvent interactions in glucose solution is greater than in urea solution. Similar results have also been reported by Parmar and coworkers⁸ for solutions of sucrose and urea in dimethyl sulphoxide + water mixed solvents. Furthermore, there is marked decrease in the value of ϕ_v^0 (Table 3) as the amount of glycine in urea + aqueous glycine mixture increases, suggesting a decreased solute-solvent interaction with the increase in glycine concentration. However, for glucose, ϕ_v^0 has lowest value in 0.02 M glycine + water mixture, indicating weakest solute-solvent interaction at this concentration of glycine. It is interesting to note that the values of S_v^* (Table 3) of urea in aqueous glycine mixtures truly support the behaviour of ϕ_v^0 . The S_v^* values for urea change from negative at lower (0.01 and 0.02 M) glycine concentration to positive at higher (0.03 M) glycine concentration, suggesting an increase in solute-solute interactions with increase in the amount of glycine. Thus, the observed increase in S_v^* , and an opposite trend in ϕ_v^0 , with increasing amount of glycine in urea + glycine + water mixture clearly justifies our earlier findings⁹. As expected, largest S_v^* value (associated with the smallest ϕ_v^0 value) for glucose in 0.02 M glycine + water mixture (Table 3) shows the presence of strongest solute-solute interaction in this glycine + water mixture. Similar trends in S_v^* are also reported for ammonium sulphate and magnesium sulphate in aqueous urea¹⁰.

The viscosity data were analysed by using the equation⁶ :

$$\eta_r = \eta/\eta_0 = 1 + AC^{1/2} + BC \quad (3)$$

where η and η_0 are the dynamic viscosities of solution and solvent respectively, η_r is the relative viscosity of the solution, A is the Falkenhagen coefficient¹¹, a measure of solute-solute interactions. B , the Jones-Dole coefficient is empirical and measures the structural modification induced by solute-solvent interactions¹².

Furthermore, the viscosity data were also examined in the light of the transition-state theory of the relative viscosity proposed by Feakins *et al.*¹³. According to this theory B -coefficient is given as

$$B = (\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0/1000 + \bar{V}_1^0(\Delta\mu_2^{0\#} - \Delta\mu_1^{0\#})/RT/1000 \quad (4)$$

where \bar{V}_1^0 and \bar{V}_2^0 are the partial molar volumes of the solvent and solute, respectively. T is the absolute temperature and R is the gas constant. The values of $\mu_1^{0\#}$ and $\mu_2^{0\#}$ were calculated using the following equations :

$$\Delta\mu_1^{0\#} = RT \ln (\eta_0 \bar{V}_1^0/hN) \quad (5)$$

and

$$\Delta\mu_2^{0\#} = \Delta\mu_1^{0\#} + (RT/\bar{V}_1^0) [1000B - (\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0)] \quad (6)$$

where h is the Planck's constant and N is the Avogadro constant. The calculated values of A , B , $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ and $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ are given in Table 4.

Table 4. Falkenhagen coefficient (A), Jones-Dole coefficient (B), free energies of activation of viscous flow per mole of solvent ($\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$) and solute ($\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$) of urea/D-glucose in aqueous glycine at 308 K

Glycine (M/mol dm ⁻³)	A (10 ⁻² dm ^{3/2} mol ^{-1/2})	B (10 ⁻² dm ³ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)
Urea + aqueous glycine				
0.01	0.8963	5.9589	8.8968	23.9479
0.02	0.7769	4.0373	8.9015	20.7562
0.03	-3.3009	4.3972	8.9383	17.1786
D-Glucose + aqueous glycine				
0.01	-5.0816	65.2550	8.9162	122.7948
0.02	13.7820	6.1100	8.9429	26.5837
0.03	-1.2422	43.7650	8.9436	84.5306

The three possible superimposed interactions taking place in the ternary systems under study are :

(1) Direct interaction between polar portion of the glycine zwitterion and the amide groups/hydroxyl groups of urea/glucose, respectively (solute-solute interactions).

(2) Hydration of glycine zwitterion (solute-solvent interactions) due to orientation of water molecules around

NH₃⁺ and COO⁻ groups of glycine.

(3) Hydration of urea amide groups/glucose hydroxyl groups (solute-solvent interactions).

The smaller values of A -coefficients as compared to B -coefficients (Table 4) for both the solutes in different solvent mixtures suggest the predominance of latter two types of interactions (glycine-water and urea/glucose-water) over the effect of the former one (glycine zwitterion-urea/glucose).

The free energy of activation of viscous flow of a solution is another useful parameter to assess the complexity of liquid structure. According to Feakins *et al.*¹³ greater the value of $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ greater is the structure making ability of the solute. The observed results (Table 4) reflect that $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ values are large as compared to $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ values for both the systems in all the three solvent mixtures, thereby suggesting that both urea and glucose behave as structure makers/promoters in the concentration range (0.01–0.03 M) of glycine + water. Similar conclusion was also arrived at by others¹⁴ from the study of transition metal chlorides in aqueous glycine. However earlier investigators reported dual role of urea as liquid structure breaker¹⁵ as well as liquid structure former¹⁶. The larger $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ values for glucose than for urea point out that glucose has greater structure making tendency than urea in aqueous glycine. Further, Table 4 reveals that there is slight increase in $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ while a significant decrease in $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ is observed as the amount of glycine in both the ternary systems increases. This again reinforces our earlier view that solute-solute interaction is more pronounced in glycine-rich mixture. Thus the results inferred from viscometric study (A , B , $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ and $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ parameters) are in good agreement with those inferred from volumetric study (ϕ_v^0 and S_v^* parameters).

For mixtures of interacting components the molar refractivity of each component is given by¹⁷

$$R_D = 4\pi\alpha N \quad (7)$$

where α is the molecular polarizability and N , the Avogadro number, is affected by the presence of other components. Thus, the study of the variation of R_D with mixture composition gives information on the interactions in the system¹⁸.

The molar refractivity, R_D of the mixtures under study can be calculated from the refractive indices, n_D by using Lorentz-Lorentz equation

$$R_D = [(n_D^2 - 1)/(n_D^2 + 2)] \left(\sum_{i=1}^3 x_i M_i / \rho \right) \quad (8)$$

where x_i and M_i are mole fraction and molecular weight of

the i -th component of the mixture, respectively. The calculated values of R_D at 308 K for the present ternary mixtures are summarized in Table 5 and plotted in Fig. 1 as a func-

Table 5. Molar refractivity (R_D) for urea/D-glucose in aqueous glycine as function of concentration (C) of ureal/D-glucose at 308 K

C (mol dm ⁻³)	R_D (10 ⁻⁶ m ³ mol ⁻¹)		
	Urea + 0.01 M glycine	Urea + 0.02 M glycine	Urea + 0.03 M glycine
0.0000	3.7099	3.7138	3.6910
0.0100	3.7187	3.7194	3.6958
0.0300	3.7227	3.7260	3.6999
0.0500	3.7260	3.7309	3.7054
0.0700	3.7341	3.7339	3.7084
0.0900	3.7422	3.7386	3.7117
0.1000	3.7455	3.7421	3.7133
C	D-Glucose + 0.01 M	D-Glucose + 0.02 M	D-Glucose + 0.03 M
	glycine	glycine	glycine
0.0000	3.7096	3.7151	3.6919
0.0100	3.7194	3.7204	3.7014
0.0300	3.7266	3.7331	3.7164
0.0500	3.7374	3.7436	3.7296
0.0700	3.7486	3.7516	3.7400
0.0900	3.7587	3.7617	3.7501
0.1000	3.7661	3.7721	3.7546

Fig. 1. Plots of molar refractivity vs urea/D-glucose concentration for urea + 0.01 M glycine (*), + 0.02 M glycine (•), + 0.03 M glycine (x); D-glucose + 0.01 M glycine (♦), + 0.02 M glycine (■), + 0.03 M glycine (▲) at 308 K.

tion of urea/glucose concentration. It is evident from Fig. 1 that R_D increases almost linearly with the increasing amount of urea/glucose in all the three glycine + water mixtures. As R_D is directly proportional to the molecular polarizability, Fig. 1 suggests that overall polarizability of both the systems under study increases with increasing amount of urea/glucose in the mixtures. The higher magnitude of R_D for glucose than for urea (Fig. 1) in all the three glycine + water mixtures is in accordance with the conclusions drawn from other results that the interactions between components in glucose + glycine + water mixture are stronger than the interactions between the components in urea + glycine + water mixture.

Experimental

Glycine (Himedia, 99.5% purity) was crystallized from ethanol + water mixture and dried at 100° under reduced pressure before being used. Urea (Glaxo, 99.5% purity) was dried over P₂O₅ in a desiccator for 72 h before use. D-Glucose (Merck, 99.5% purity) was used as such. The binary solvent mixtures (mixed solvent) (0.01, 0.02 and 0.03 M) glycine + water were prepared using doubly distilled, deionized water and were used as solvents to prepare solutions of 0.01, 0.03, 0.05, 0.07, 0.09 and 0.1 M urea and D-glucose. Care was taken in order to obtain stable, clear and dust-free samples. The samples were stored in dark to minimize biological and photochemical degradation. The weighings were done on an Afcoset ER-120A electronic balance with a precision of ±0.1 mg.

Densities of mixed solvents and solutions of urea/glucose in these solvents were measured using a single-stem pycnometer of bulb capacity 8×10^{-3} dm³ with graduated marks on the stem. The marks on the stem were calibrated using doubly distilled water. For viscosity measurements Cannon Ubbelohde¹⁷ type viscometer was employed. The pycnometer and viscometer containing test liquid were kept for about 25 min in an electronically controlled thermostatic water bath so that thermal fluctuation was minimized. The accuracy in density and viscosity measurements was found to be ±0.01 kg m⁻³ and 3×10^{-6} N m⁻² s, respectively. Refractive indices were measured with the help of a thermostated Abbe-refractometer. Calibration of the instrument was done by measuring the refractive indices of doubly distilled water and toluene at known temperatures²⁰. The sample mixtures were directly injected into the prism assembly of the instrument by means of an airtight hypodermic syringe. When the liquid mixtures attained constant temperature, the refractive index measurements were made. The error in refractive index measurements was less than ±0.0001 unit. The temperature of the solutions was main-

tained at 308 ± 0.05 K in an electronically controlled thermostatic water bath.

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